

TODAY'S STATE OF THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Today, a favorable investment environment is a necessary condition for ensuring stable high development of the economy, attracting investments to regions and industries, and increasing entrepreneurial activity. It serves the inflow of foreign direct investments into important production and social projects, expands the possibilities of innovation, and increases the quality of socio-economic development. During the years of independence, Uzbekistan went through a complex stage of structural transformation of the entire economy, which was accompanied by certain difficulties in terms of developing the appropriate concept and mechanisms for its implementation. It should be recognized that specific issues in the field of doing business (for example, currency conversion, involvement of international financial institutions, etc.) have not been resolved for a long time, and this, in turn, has a serious impact on the country's investment potential. However, in the following years, the situation in this regard began to change radically, with reforms aimed at improving the investment environment becoming dynamic. The implementation of structural reforms aimed at improving the business environment helps achieve positive results, including:

Reduction of deadlines, the number of documents, and costs related to business registration;

Liberalization of the foreign exchange market, removal of restrictions on the repatriation of profits;

Simplification of tax and customs administration, introduction of a risk analysis system, reduction of documents and time required for customs clearance;

Execution of contracts (introduction of mediation institution), strengthening of measures for the protection of minority shareholders, etc.

Every country, first of all, strives for economic development to join the ranks of developed countries in the world. In this way, it seeks to develop the macro and micro environment and increase gross domestic product. Attracting foreign investments is also very important for such large-scale works. In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026, there are a number of

goals to further improve the investment environment in the country and increase its attractiveness, and tasks are provided.

Including: In the 26th goal of the development strategy, it is planned to further improve the investment environment in the country and increase its attractiveness, to take measures to attract 120 billion US dollars, including 70 billion dollars of foreign investments, in the next five years.[1].

In the address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, to the Oliy Majlis on December 21, 2022, "Our economy received 8 billion dollars of direct foreign investments this year, and our exports are 19 billion, admitting that it reached the sixth priority in 2023 to further improve the conditions for increasing local and foreign private investments in the economy [2]." This indicates the need to further increase the attractiveness of the favorable investment climate for foreign investments. Investment in the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to the decree of the President of our country, Sh. Mirziyoyev, dated August 2, 2018, "On measures to radically improve the investment environment in the Republic of Uzbekistan," was adopted in order to increase the attractiveness of the investment environment. Foreign citizens and stateless persons who entered the Republic of Uzbekistan were granted the right to receive a multiple-entry three-year visa and to extend its validity for an unlimited amount without the need to leave the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Article 9 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Foreign Economic Activity" defines the task of attracting foreign investments to the republic as one of the main directions of foreign economic activity. Precisely for this reason, investing in the economy of Uzbekistan, first of all, at the expense of mobilizing domestic resources, intensive modernization of important sectors of our economy, technical and technological re-equipment, further development of the transport and communication sector, and social construction of infrastructure facilities has become a decisive priority [3], and this determines the relevance of the studied topic. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities" states that "investments are tangible and intangible assets invested by the investor in the social sphere, entrepreneurship, scientific and other types of activities based on risks for the purpose of profit and the rights to them, including the rights to intellectual property objects, as well as reinvestments" [4].

As far as we know, the activity of foreign investors mainly consists of business activities aimed at earning income and acquiring all kinds of tangible

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and intangible assets and related rights, including intellectual property rights, which are not prohibited by law. Any income from investments is considered foreign investment. Ensuring a favorable investment climate and enhancing its attractiveness in our country is an urgent task today. Therefore, it is desirable to increase the state's attractiveness by creating a favorable investment climate to attract investment. Economists D.G. Gozibekov, A.V. Vakhobov, Sh.Kh. Khajibakiyev, M.A. Raimjonova, N.G. Muminov, B.S. Mamatov, Sh.I. Mustafakulov, B. Salimov, I. Khotamov, and D.Y. Khojamkulov have devoted their scientific works to studying the attractiveness of the investment environment and the challenges of attracting foreign investments to the national economy.

According to the data of the State Statistics Committee, investments in fixed capital in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021 were as follows: total investments in fixed capital - 245 trillion soums, centralized investments - 44.8 trillion soums, decentralized investments - 200.2 trillion soums, foreign investment and loans allocated to fixed capital - 104.5 trillion soums, foreign loans under the guarantee of the Republic of Uzbekistan - 17.3 trillion soums, direct foreign investment and loans - 87.2 trillion soums. Today, more than 50 countries are investing in the economy of Uzbekistan. According to information given by Alexey Sim, the deputy head of the strategic development agency, in an interview with the "Economic Review" publication, the following countries invested the most in Uzbekistan in 2021: China - 2.2 billion dollars; Russia - 2.1 billion dollars; Turkey - 1.18 billion dollars; Germany - 800.7 million dollars; South Korea - 137.4 million dollars. By the end of 2021, the volume of foreign investments was 11.1 billion dollars, which is 113% of the annual forecast, including investments in fixed capital reaching 9.8 billion dollars (110% growth rate compared to 2020 figures). Foreign direct investment (FDI) and loans amounted to \$9 billion, or 117 percent over forecast, including \$8.2 billion in fixed capital, a 124 percent increase over 2020.

In conclusion, it should be noted that one of the important issues is to study the experience of developed countries, the laws, and decisions adopted by the country to improve the investment environment, and apply their necessary aspects to the conditions of Uzbekistan. The implementation of these proposals and recommendations will allow for the expansion of the attraction of foreign investments in the economy of our republic.

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